

Supplementary Material for:
Text-based Geolocation with a Byte-level Language Model

Mikhail Orzhenovskii, Alina Pak, Roman Kane and Arina Razmyslovich

Yachay AI

ORCID (Mikhail Orzhenovskii): <https://orcid.org/0000-0003-2811-6294>, ORCID (Roman Kane):
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-1524-2999>

Abstract. Geotagging, the process of assigning geographical coordinates to text, has found a wide range of applications, from disaster management to public health surveillance. Contrary to the prior focus on user-level predictions and platform-specific data, this study emphasizes tweet-level geolocation using text content. We present a method combining hierarchical agglomerative clustering with classification, employing a byte-level transformer model trained on a multi-lingual dataset. Our approach, evaluated for its efficacy in selecting the top 10% of geographically relevant tweets, achieves a Median Error of 15 km and a Mean Error of 403 km, significantly surpassing existing methods by margins of 560 km and 2314 km, respectively, as demonstrated in Table 3. Moreover, we investigate uncertainty estimation techniques in multi-class classification for transformer models, an underexplored area in geotagging research. Although some methods show potential, achieving oracle-level accuracy remains a challenge. Our work extends the field of geotagging by focusing on text-only tweet-level predictions and provides valuable insights into uncertainty estimation methods for transformer models in this domain.

Notice

This is supplementary material for the paper "Text-based Geolocation with a Byte-level Language Model", accepted at ECAI 2024. The main paper should be considered the primary reference. This supplementary material is made available for additional details, extended results, or other information that could not be included in the main paper due to space constraints.

A Additional Material

Top-30 Languages

Figure 1: Language distribution of tweets in the combined dataset. Counts are presented in log scale.

Top-30 Locations

Figure 2: Location distribution of tweets in the combined dataset. Counts are presented in log scale.

Figure 3: Language-location distribution for top languages except English

Figure 4: Calibration chart for Softmax Confidence

Figure 5: Architectural Diagram

B Training schedule

Our primary model has 222M parameters, and the scaled-down half-sized model has 113M parameters. We set aside a 5% stratified random subsample of the dataset for validation. For training the half-sized model, we removed the bottom 25% of data samples in terms of accuracy, as identified by the primary model, to reduce noise and enhance efficiency.

Hyperparameter tuning was guided by manual experimentation and focused on Median Error (km) for the top 10% confidence-based tweets as the target metric. Table 1 outlines the chosen hyperparameters. The model was trained for two epochs, with learning rates of 1×10^{-4} and 1×10^{-5} for the first and second epochs, respectively.

The selection of hyperparameters for training was made following a series of manual experiments. The hyperparameter search space is depicted in Table 1, and we used Median Error (km) for the top 10% confidence-based tweets as the target metric. The model underwent training for a span of two epochs. For the first epoch, we used a learning rate of 1×10^{-4} , and for the second epoch, the learning rate was decreased to 1×10^{-5} . We employed the Adam optimizer for our training process.

Training was executed on a single NVIDIA GeForce RTX 4090 GPU, taking approximately 72 hours. The full-sized model was trained with a batch size of 48, while the half-sized model used a batch size of 96. Using the same hardware, the model is capable of inference at a rate of 512 samples per second with a batch size of 128.

We used the ByT5 implementation from Huggingface Transformers[7], building our custom training loop and validation on the PyTorch framework.

C Case Studies: Examples of Predictions

To provide a nuanced understanding of the model’s performance, we examine both correct and incorrect predictions in specific cases.

C.1 Correct Predictions

- **Example 1: (in Mongolian)**

Өнгөрсөн жилийн хичнэл сургуулийг шалтгаангүй 2 сараар хаасан хүмүүст хариуцлага тооцохымсон.

öngörsön jiliin khichnel surguuliig shaltgaangüi 2 saraar khaasan khümüüst khariutslaga tootsokhymson.

‘Those who closed schools for 2 months without reason last year will be held accountable.’

The text was correctly placed in Mongolia. However, it serves as an example of bias as it does not contain a location reference. In our corpus, approximately 80% of Mongolian tweets originate from Mongolia. While this doesn’t significantly affect accuracy, it doesn’t align with our expectations. We plan to address this bias in future releases.

- **Example 2: (in English)**

worst place I ever been in Vienna

The text was correctly placed in Vienna, as it explicitly mentions the location.

- **Example 3: (in Spanish)**

hoy tenemos 12°C con cielo parcialmente nublado en siero asturias. ¡adios febrero

Hoy tenemos doce grados Celsius con cielo parcialmente nublado en Siero Asturias. ¡Adios febrero!

‘today we have 12°C with partly cloudy sky in siero asturias. goodbye february’

The text was placed in Gijón, Spain, but was posted from Colunga, Spain, which is only 33 kilometers away. The named entity “Siero Asturias” likely contributed to this accurate prediction.

C.2 Incorrect Predictions

- **Example 1: (in English)**

since covid its like grenadian government get shtupid

The text was predicted to be from Grenada but was actually posted from Canada.

- **Example 2: (in English)**

fort lauderdale west palm or delray beach

The text mentions locations in Florida but was posted from Canada.

- **Example 3: (in Arabic)**

جواز ي عطي ني ال غنوشي # عن د ي ستوس طلي شكون ال يونان # في التونسية الجالية ن زور ن حب ، خاص سفر هاذي ال سخانة في علي هم ن طمان shukuwn yastawsitli eind #alghanushi yuetini jawaz safar khasin , nuhibu nazur aljaliat altuwnisiat fi #alyunan nitman ealayhim fi alsikhanat hadhi ‘Who is asking me when #Ghannouchi gives me a special passport, we would like to visit the Tunisian community in #Greece and check on them in this heat.’

The tweet mentions Tunisia and Greece but was posted from the United States. The model predicted Tunisia.

D Monte Carlo Dropout Uncertainty

Aggregation Methods: We examined two primary approaches for aggregating predictions from multiple MCD runs:

1. **Average Prediction (pred-avg):** Probabilities for each class are computed using softmax over the logits for each MCD run. The final class prediction is obtained by averaging these probabilities across all runs and selecting the class with the highest average probability.
2. **Voting Mechanism (pred-vote):** The class appearing most frequently across MCD runs is selected using a majority voting strategy.

Confidence Metrics: To quantify the uncertainty and thereby the confidence in our predictions, we introduce three metrics:

Table 1: Hyperparameter Search Space

Hyperparameter name	Chosen value	Search space
Initial learning rate	1×10^{-4}	$2 \times 10^{-4}, 1 \times 10^{-4}, 5 \times 10^{-5}, 2 \times 10^{-5}$
Number of epochs	2	1, 2, 3, 4
Batch size	48	32, 48
Label smoothing factor	0.2	0.0, 0.1, 0.2, 0.3, 0.4, 0.5
Cluster count	3000	1000, 3000, 6000

1. **Max Standard Deviation (std-max):** This captures the highest standard deviation observed across the class probabilities over multiple MCD runs.
2. **Standard Deviation of Selected Class (std-pred):** This measures the standard deviation of the probability associated with the chosen class, across all MCD runs.
3. **Max Probability Uncertainty (max-probs-uncertainty):** This metric evaluates the standard deviation of the highest probability class from each MCD run, offering insights into the model’s most confident predictions.

E Data Preprocessing Details

Given the inherent noise and irregularities associated with social media data, we executed preprocessing steps to improve data quality:

- We converted all text to lowercase to avoid treating words with different casing as distinct entities (e.g., treating "Paris" and "paris" as equivalent).
- Usernames were removed to adhere to privacy considerations.
- Punctuation was removed since it does not provide meaningful information for our NLP task.
- URL links were removed as they are often shortened and lack useful information.
- Trailing whitespaces were removed to prevent tokenization issues and reduce noise.
- Hashtags were normalized (e.g., #brazilcool becomes "brazilcool") to convert them into meaningful words rather than treating them as separate entities.
- Tweets consisting solely of punctuation, numbers, special characters, or emojis were removed due to noise and lack of useful information.

F Uncertainty estimation

Given that a significant portion of tweets lack explicit geotagging features, we aim to identify tweets that are most likely to contain relevant geographical information. Based on human evaluations, we set a target of confidently geotagging the top 10% of tweets. We used Krippendorff’s Alpha to assess inter-annotator agreement as we had 3 internal annotators. The Krippendorff’s Alpha among the annotators was 0.83. Our chosen fraction is higher to account for potential indirect geographic cues present in tweets, in addition to those with explicitly stated locations. We employ several techniques for uncertainty estimation: Softmax Confidence, Relative Probability Methods, Variance-Based Confidence, Entropy-Based Selection, Auxiliary Confidence Classifier and Monte Carlo Dropout Uncertainty. Each method employs a different statistical measure to rank the confidence of a model’s prediction.

F.1 Softmax Confidence

Confidence is defined as the maximum value among the output probabilities derived from the softmax function applied to the model’s logits.

$$P(i) = \frac{e^{\frac{\text{logits}_i}{T}}}{\sum_j e^{\frac{\text{logits}_j}{T}}}$$

The samples are selected by ordering them by descending $P(i)$.

This method has been explored by Geifman and El-Yaniv [1] and Guo et al. [2]. While softmax does not reflect true probabilities until calibrated, it still can be used to select the most confident predictions.

F.2 Relative Probability Methods

We introduce two alternative confidence measures that extend beyond simply using the maximum probability after the softmax operation. The first approach employs the difference between the highest and the second-highest softmax probabilities. The second approach utilizes the ratio between the highest and second-highest probabilities. Both methods produce results that are comparable to using the softmax probabilities directly.

F.3 Variance-Based Confidence

We can also sort the samples by the variance of the output probabilities. Lower variance corresponds to higher confidence.

F.4 Entropy-Based Selection

We also explored using entropy as a confidence measure for sample selection. Entropy $H(P)$ for a discrete probability distribution P is computed as:

$$H(P) = - \sum_i P(i) \log(P(i)) \tag{1}$$

Samples are then ranked by their entropy values, with the top 10% selected for further processing. However, this method did not yield results superior to those obtained through softmax-based selection.

F.5 Auxiliary Model as Confidence Classifier

We experimented with treating confidence prediction as a binary classification task, using a part of the validation set labeled with correct (1) and incorrect (0) predictions from the primary model. Two models were considered: a character-level

convolutional neural network (CharCNN) and a linear layer appended to a frozen encoder block of the primary model.

Despite their computational efficiency, both methods lagged in accuracy when compared to softmax-based selection. Employing a full-size auxiliary model could potentially improve accuracy but would unacceptably double the computational load during inference.

Note: The idea of framing this as a regression task—predicting the logarithm of the error in kilometers—is left for future exploration.

F.6 Monte Carlo Dropout Uncertainty

Monte Carlo Dropout (MCD) provides a powerful technique for uncertainty estimation that permits the use of pre-trained transformer models, unlike other methods such as Bayesformer [5] and CUE [4] which necessitate training from scratch. Despite its computational cost due to multiple forward passes during inference, MCD offers valuable insights into model confidence.

Performance Evaluation: We select the top 10% of samples based on a descending order of confidence metrics to evaluate the model’s performance. The uncertainty was measured as highest standard deviation observed over 25 MCD runs, for the class that was predicted most frequently. This combination of aggregation and confidence metric was best performing. The other aggregation methods and confidence metrics for MCD are described in Appendix D.

Comparison with Other Work: Consistent with the findings of Holm et al. [3], our results indicate that MCD does not outperform the softmax method for our particular problem. For computational efficiency, the algorithm proposed by Vazhentsev et al. [6] shows promise; however, it still does not surpass the speed of softmax-based methods due to the intrinsic need for multiple forward passes.

F.7 Comparative Evaluation of Methods

In this section, we assess various methodologies for selecting the top 10% of samples based on the highest confidence levels. Our evaluations reveal that the softmax approach delivers the best performance among all the methods tested. The results are listed in Table 2.

For benchmarking, we introduce an ‘Oracle’ scenario where confidence levels are inversely related to the prediction errors, thereby ensuring that the most accurate predictions are included in the top 10%. Although none of the methods tested have achieved scores close to the Oracle’s benchmark, this gap underscores the room for further improvements in our confidence estimation techniques.

The model underpinning our experiments is a 12-layer ByT5 architecture, and all evaluations are performed on the evaluation subset of our dataset.

G Detailed Human Evaluation Process

G.1 Human Evaluation for Geotagging Accuracy

A critical aspect of our study involved human evaluators assessing the accuracy of tweet geotagging. The primary objective was to ascertain each tweet’s potential to enable city-level or finer estimation of the user’s current location.

G.2 Annotation Process

Three internal annotators were selected. Prior to the evaluation, each annotator underwent training, which included a clear set of instructions aimed at guiding their assessment process. The instruction was, “Your goal is to assess tweets to determine if they contain sufficient geographical information to accurately estimate the user’s current location at a city level or more precise. Focus solely on the present location details, ignoring past or future location mentions. For each tweet, decide whether it provides explicit or implicit geographical cues—like city names, landmarks, or local events enough to pinpoint the city or a more specific location. Assign ‘Yes’ if the tweet allows for such city-level geolocation, and ‘No’ if it lacks adequate cues for geolocation”. This directive was intended to standardize the evaluation process across all annotators, ensuring consistency in their approach to identifying geographically informative tweets.

G.3 Examples and Guidelines

To further support the annotators in their task, a series of examples were provided alongside the instructions. These examples were carefully chosen to illustrate the variety of tweets that could meet the evaluation criteria. For example, a tweet saying, “I’ve been living in city X for 10 years, and have never seen this before,” served as a clear example of a tweet containing explicit geographical details sufficient for city-level geotagging.

G.4 Labeling Criteria

The labeling process was designed to be straightforward, with annotators asked to assign one of two categorical labels to each tweet. This binary categorization process was predicated on the annotator’s judgment of whether a tweet provided sufficient geographical information to accurately discern the user’s current location to a city-level degree of precision or finer.

G.5 Quality Control: Krippendorff’s Alpha

To ensure the reliability and consistency of the annotations, we measured inter-annotator agreement using Krippendorff’s Alpha. The high agreement score of 0.83 among the annotators indicated a strong consensus, validating the effectiveness of the training and the clarity of the instructions provided.

G.6 Implications for Geotagging Tweets

The human evaluation process played a critical role in establishing the ground truth for our study. The results from this process were essential for setting the target of confidently geotagging the top 10% of tweets and for training and assessing the performance of our uncertainty estimation models.

Table 2: Relevancy Filtering Results

Method Name	MAE (top 10%), km	Median Error (top 10%), km
Softmax Confidence	403.43	14.85
Relative Probability	527.47	10.64
Variance-Based Confidence	467.98	22.93
Entropy-Based Selection	464.67	22.93
Auxiliary Model (CharCNN)	487.03	29.40
Auxiliary Model (Frozen ByT5)	565.56	53.03
Monte Carlo Dropout	508.80	11.78
Oracle (best possible metrics)	4.3	1.4

References

- [1] Y. Geifman and R. El-Yaniv. Selective classification for deep neural networks. In *Proceedings of the 31st International Conference on Neural Information Processing Systems, NIPS'17*, page 4885–4894, Red Hook, NY, USA, 2017. Curran Associates Inc. ISBN 9781510860964.
- [2] C. Guo, G. Pleiss, Y. Sun, and K. Q. Weinberger. On calibration of modern neural networks. In D. Precup and Y. W. Teh, editors, *Proceedings of the 34th International Conference on Machine Learning*, volume 70 of *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, pages 1321–1330. PMLR, 06–11 Aug 2017. URL <https://proceedings.mlr.press/v70/guo17a.html>.
- [3] A. N. Holm, D. Wright, and I. Augenstein. Revisiting softmax for uncertainty approximation in text classification. *Information*, 14(7), 2023. ISSN 2078-2489. doi: 10.3390/info14070420.
- [4] J. Li, Z. Sun, B. Liang, L. Gui, and Y. He. CUE: An uncertainty interpretation framework for text classifiers built on pre-trained language models. In R. J. Evans and I. Shpitser, editors, *Proceedings of the Thirty-Ninth Conference on Uncertainty in Artificial Intelligence*, volume 216 of *Proceedings of Machine Learning Research*, pages 1253–1262. PMLR, 31 Jul–04 Aug 2023.
- [5] K. A. Sankararaman, S. Wang, and H. Fang. Bayesformer: Transformer with uncertainty estimation, 2022.
- [6] A. Vazhentsev, G. Kuzmin, A. Shelmanov, A. Tsvigun, E. Tsymbalov, K. Fedyanin, M. Panov, A. Panchenko, G. Gusev, M. Burtsev, M. Avetisian, and L. Zhukov. Uncertainty estimation of transformer predictions for misclassification detection. In *Proceedings of the 60th Annual Meeting of the Association for Computational Linguistics (Volume 1: Long Papers)*, pages 8237–8252, Dublin, Ireland, May 2022. Association for Computational Linguistics. doi: 10.18653/v1/2022.acl-long.566.
- [7] T. Wolf, L. Debut, V. Sanh, J. Chaumond, C. Delangue, A. Moi, P. Cistac, T. Rault, R. Louf, M. Funtowicz, J. Davison, S. Shleifer, P. von Platen, C. Ma, Y. Jernite, J. Plu, C. Xu, T. Le Scao, S. Gugger, M. Drame, Q. Lhoest, and A. Rush. Transformers: State-of-the-art natural language processing. In *Proceedings of the 2020 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing: System Demonstrations*, pages 38–45, Online, Oct. 2020. Association for Computational Linguistics. doi: 10.18653/v1/2020.emnlp-demos.6. URL <https://aclanthology.org/2020.emnlp-demos.6>.